

Thermodynamic Formation Constants of Coinage Metal Chelates of Azelaic Acid

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Manuscript received 9 October 1972; revised 14 February 1974; accepted 4 April 1974

Metal ligand stability constants of copper and gold with azelaic acid were determined potentiometrically at 25° in aqueous media, in five different ionic strengths of 0.125M, 0.1M, 0.075M, 0.05M and 0.025M NaClO₄. Free energy values have also been evaluated.

THE stability constants can be used to predict the conditions required for complete formation of the given complex. Reliable information of this type is of great importance in planning analytical and separative procedures. In consequence, complex formation of coinage metals and some transition metals have been studied by us with oxygen donor ligands.¹⁻⁴ In this paper we have reported the study of copper and gold complexes of azelaic acid. Calculations have been made as in our earlier publication.¹ Thermodynamic formation constants have also been determined and free energy values have been evaluated therefrom.

Experimental

For the investigations of metal-ligand equilibria, it becomes necessary to control the free ligand concentration in order that various equations can be applied. This can be achieved either by changing the total ligand concentration or by varying the total acid in the system by the addition either of an acid or of an alkali. Irving and Rossotti⁵ described a procedure in which a mixture of the acidified solution of metal ion and the ligand was titrated against an alkali. Method of Bjerrum⁶ and Calvin⁷ (*pH* titration technique) has been applied in our present investigations. The method provides proton-ligand stability constants of the ligand and these are employed for the calculation of the metal ligand stability constant. Hence from a single set of experiments all the variables are obtained

Solutions: Calculated amount of azelaic acid (recrystallised) was dissolved in double distilled water to give 0.1M solution.

Solutions of copper (II) sulphate (B.D.H. Analar), and gold (III) chloride (Judex) were standardised by usual classical methods⁸ and were diluted to give 0.01M solutions.

Carbon dioxide free sodium hydroxide (B.D.H., Analar) solution was prepared (0.1M) and standardised by potentiometric titration against standard oxalic acid solution. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel)

was employed for maintaining ionic strengths and the solution of required strength (1.0M) was prepared by dilution. The required solution (0.1M) of perchloric acid was prepared by suitable dilution of the original acid (Riedel).

A mains operated Philips *pH*-meter, which has least count of 0.05 *pH* unit was employed for *pH* measurements. Electrode system consisted of a glass electrode designed for use over the entire *pH*-range 0 to 14 and a saturated calomel electrode. The *pH*-meter was standardised before and after each titration with buffer solutions of *pH* 4.00 and 9.27.

All the experiments in the present work were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions, at a constant temperature of 25°. Measurements were carried out with solutions maintaining five different ionic strengths of 0.125M, 0.1M, 0.075M, 0.05M and 0.025M which were achieved by adding the necessary amount of 1.0M NaClO₄ solution.

Titration curves were drawn as already described¹ and titration curves drawn (Figure. 1).

Fig. 1. Titration curves of copper and Gold-Azelaic acid Chelates
A-HClO₄(0.005M), B-Azelaic acid (0.005M)
C-Cu(0.001M), D-Au(0.001 M)

Results and Discussion

A graph between *pH* and volume of alkali required for the corresponding *pH* change was plotted. A displacement in the metal titration curve with respect to the ligand titration curve indicated that as complexation with ligand takes place there is liberation of protons. Also the colour change at certain *pH* gave evidence of coloured complex formation. Since the solutions employed were dilute, the probability of existence of hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing complexes and the complexes with anions present can reasonably be considered to be negligible under the experimental conditions of our present investigation and have been ignored. The hydrolysis of metal ion is accompanied by liberation of protons, and as such a displacement of metal titration curve is possible even in the absence of any reaction with the reagent. In order to avoid this error all calculations were done below the *pH* at which any precipitate occurred. \bar{n} and *pL* values were obtained from previous equations¹ and graph of \bar{n} vs *pL* (known as the formation curve) were plotted. Formation constants were evaluated with the help of protonation constant calculated earlier².

Copper (II) azelaic acid system : The plot of \bar{n} vs *pL* for the complex indicates that the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of 2 (Fig. 2). This suggests that

Fig. 2. Formation curves of Cu-Azelaic Acid chelate. A-0.125M, B-0.1M, C-0.075M, D-0.05M, E-0.025M

copper forms two types of complexes in the proportion of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with the ligand. The copper ligand solution changed to light blue from the initial colourless between *pH* 5.0-5.4. This is the *pH* which corresponds approximately to \bar{n} value of 0.5, suggesting that the first complex formed was blue coloured. Since this colour continued and \bar{n} values went upto 2 it is concluded that both the complexes formed were of blue colour. The formation constants were calculated by interpolation at half \bar{n} values, and also by least square method and are tabulated

in Table 1.

The values of step constants (Table 1) show that there is not much difference in the magnitude of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ which may be interpreted to mean that the formation of the two chelate species are not independent. In literature only K_1 values of copper chelates with malonic, succinic and glutaric acids have been reported.

Gold (III) azelaic acid system : During the course of titration of the metal-ligand against alkali no specific colour change was observed, only the initial light yellow colour became faint as the *pH* increases. Three complexes appear to be formed in this case, as the values of \bar{n} in the formation curves (Figure 3) extended upto 3 at all ionic-strengths. Formation constants were calculated by interpolation at half \bar{n} values; other methods were not found to be applicable. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values differ sufficiently to suggest that the formation of chelate species were quite independent, but the small difference between $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ values shows that the chelate

Fig. 3. Formation curves of Au-Azelaic Acid chelate A-0.125M, B-3.1M, C-0.075M, D-0.05M, E-0.025M

species were formed simultaneously. The formation constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu(II), Au(III)-CHELATES OF AZELAIC ACID

Metal	Constants	Method	Ionic-Strengths				
			0.125	0.1	0.075	0.05	0.025
Cu	log K_1	(I)	3.62	3.94	4.22	4.46	4.74
		(II)	3.39	3.69	4.00	4.29	4.47
	log K_2	mean	3.50	3.81	4.11	4.37	4.60
		(I)	2.94	3.06	3.26	3.48	3.78
		(II)	3.09	3.19	3.47	3.64	4.01
		log β	mean	3.01	3.12	3.36	3.56
(I)	6.56		7.00	7.48	7.96	8.52	
Au	log K_1	(I)	6.52	6.94	7.47	7.94	8.50
		(II)	5.28	5.44	5.58	5.68	5.90
	log K_2	(I)	3.80	4.08	4.42	4.76	4.94
	log K_3	(I)	3.42	3.58	3.92	4.06	4.36
	log β	(I)	12.50	13.10	13.92	14.50	15.20

(I) interpolation at half n values.
 (II) least square method.

Thermodynamic Stability constants and free energies :

In order to find the stepwise formation constants, as well as ligational standard free energy change, the experiments were carried out at 25° and five different ionic strengths.

In the present investigation, the thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolation of measured formation constants to zero ionic strengths. Ligational standard free energy was obtained from

$$\Delta F^\circ = 2.303 RT \log K^{\mu=0}$$

where $K^{\mu=0}$ is value of formation constant at zero ionic strength by extrapolation. Values of log step formation constants at various ionic strengths, extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic formation constant. These values have

been shown in Table 2 as log $K_1^{\mu=0}$, log $K_2^{\mu=0}$ and log $K_3^{\mu=0}$. Their sum has been shown as calculated log $K^{\mu=0}$. The values of overall concentration formation constant β at various ionic strengths were likewise extrapolated to zero ionic strength and the overall thermodynamic formation constants thus obtained have been symbolised as experimental log $K^{\mu=0}$.

TABLE 2.—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES AT 25°C OF Cu(II) AND Au(III) WITH AZELAIC ACID

	Metals	
	Cu	Au
log $K_1^{\mu=0}$	4.92	6.04
log $K_2^{\mu=0}$	4.12	5.28
log $K_3^{\mu=0}$	—	4.60
Calcd. log $K^{\mu=0}$	9.04	15.92
Exptl. log $K^{\mu=0}$	8.98	15.82
ΔF_1 , Kcal/mole	— 6.73	— 8.23
ΔF_2 , Kcal/mole	— 5.62	— 7.20
ΔF_3 , Kcal/mole	—	— 6.27
Calcd. ΔF° , Kcal/mole	—12.35	—21.70
Exptl. ΔF° , Kcal/mole	—12.26	—21.55

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